

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH ON THE APPLICATION OF TPACK TECHNOLOGY IN COLLEGE TEACHING

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Abstract

Under the guidance of the 13th Five Year Plan, the application of TPACK can effectively activate traditional education models, accelerate educational transformation, expand educational horizons, increase educational diversity, and better meet the needs of society for more advanced knowledge and services. It also helps to establish a "Double First Class" system, thereby improving the educational level of universities and ultimately achieving the goal of a smart campus.

Keywords: TPACK; Higher Education; Quality of education and teaching

1. Introduction

Due to the advancement of technology, high-tech has become an important technology applied to all industries in the industry, and its role cannot be ignored. Especially in the education industry, it not only involves general knowledge, but also involves more practice. Therefore, it faces more challenges and requires more proactive measures to accelerate educational transformation and achieve higher levels of educational effectiveness. The 13th Five Year Plan also provides guidance for this. In order to promote the development of universities and restore traditional educational models, we must closely combine theoretical research, creative thinking, and practical applications.

1.2. The Role of Teachers in the Age of Artificial Intelligence

With the development of modern science, more and more people have the opportunity to acquire and share knowledge through modern information technology, which has brought about revolutionary changes in the field of education in the future. Vice Minister of Education Du Zhanyuan stated that with the development of science, more and more scholars have higher learning levels and better literacy. By utilizing advanced information technology and creative thinking, teachers can convey knowledge to students in the most precise way, thereby benefiting them greatly. Teachers not only possess rich professional literacy, but also must possess excellent classroom performance and practical operations, as well as good information collection and analysis abilities. Through continuous reform and improvement, university teachers can provide high-quality courses and eliminate low-quality courses, thereby creating more competitive, creative, and challenging high-quality courses.

2. Education Informationization Teaching

With the progress of technology, information technology has deeply influenced our teaching mode. Nowadays, we can improve our abilities by using various emerging technologies such as MOOCs, flipped

classrooms, micro classes, virtual reality, mobile learning, educational informatization, intelligent education, and makers. In the current era of artificial intelligence, teachers must be more actively involved in educational reform in order to better adapt to market competition. The philosophy of 'the only constant is change' also illustrates this point. Director Wu Yan emphasized that the diversity of higher education should be actively expanded to meet the society's demand for high-quality talents, combining modern information technology with traditional education and teaching, strengthening the quality of education and teaching, and enhancing teachers' educational abilities to meet the society's demand for high-quality talents.

2.1. The Impact of TPACK on Teachers

Based on a questionnaire survey of TPACK among teachers in five universities in Urumqi, Zhou Haitao emphasized that teachers can enhance the various elements of TPACK among university teachers by strengthening self-reflection and creating a teacher teaching community. [3] Ren Xiuhua and Ren Fei constructed a TPACK knowledge structure framework for university teachers based on the knowledge structure characteristics of university teachers. Through a survey questionnaire, they analyzed the correlation between teaching experience, training frequency, teacher education background, and TPACK of university teachers. Based on the TPACK structure characteristics presented in the research results, they proposed to enhance teachers' TPACK ability by conducting diversified training, developing situational learning activities, and building collaborative groups, Promote the professional development of in-service teachers and the training of pre-service teachers. [4] In the era of artificial intelligence, professional and disciplinary construction should pay more attention to innovative concepts, and curriculum construction should be more open and transparent. So, how to continuously improve the teaching effectiveness of higher education and evaluate students' learning outcomes is worth our attention.

2.2. TPACK Introduction

Since the 1990s, due to the popularization of information technology, Punya Mishra and Matthew J. Koehler at Michigan State University in the United States have borrowed Schulman's learning theory and developed this new teaching method, which combines knowledge and methods organically to achieve optimal teaching results. TPACK, as a comprehensive educational tool, aims to help teachers better understand and apply the skills they possess, thereby enhancing their overall quality. It not only helps teachers better master the required knowledge, but also helps them better apply these technologies to improve the quality of their teaching.

Through in-depth exploration of TPACK, teachers can better grasp and apply the most advanced educational concepts, thereby better guiding the classroom. The composition of TPACK includes three main parts: TK, CK, PK [5], which form a complete curriculum system, and the four parts are PCK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK [6]. These four parts form a complete curriculum system, which can help teachers better grasp the course content and better apply the latest educational concepts.

With the development of artificial intelligence, the role of teachers has also undergone significant changes, and their responsibilities have become increasingly complex. The TPACK framework advocates that teachers should be familiar with both the theory of the curriculum and relevant technologies, and combine these knowledge to adapt to the current educational environment. This method can not only demonstrate the professional level of teachers, but also enable them to achieve the best classroom effect.

3. Modernized teaching mode of education

3.1. Deauthoritative Role of Teachers

As a teacher, we need to be more actively involved in the classroom and guide, motivate, coordinate, and cultivate students' independence through intelligent methods, so that their thinking can be fully cultivated. We also need to dare to challenge traditional teaching methods and encourage them to establish a good atmosphere of communication, cooperation, and mutual growth with others.

3.2. Students Expect to Teach Students According to Their Aptitude

Teachers not only need to impart a lesson plan to first level students, but also have a deep understanding of students' learning characteristics, and combine various educational resources such as MOOC and micro courses to provide targeted and efficient guidance, thus achieving an organic combination of education and teaching.

3.3. Backward teaching methods of teachers

With the development of technology, the blackboards, chalk, projectors, and other traditional educational resources in the classroom cannot meet the demand for high-quality courses in today's society. Therefore, it is crucial for teachers to utilize emerging technologies such as the internet and mobile devices to improve the quality and effectiveness of their courses. In today's fast-paced information society, one class is enough time to impart a complex concept to everyone.

However, how can we utilize limited resources on the internet to transform the energy of one class into an effective micro class to meet current needs and gain recognition from students?

3.4. Education and research capabilities need to be improved

Teachers should actively explore new teaching methods, combining the latest scientific knowledge with practice, in order to enable students to better grasp the latest developments in the subject. They should play a dual role as educators and Sub-I, constantly exploring the reform of classroom teaching to enhance their research capabilities. Teachers should not only teach professional courses, but also strive to cultivate students' skills in literature search, analysis, and practical writing.

3.5. Education evaluation methods need to be improved

By introducing various educational measurement tools, such as intelligent assessment and multimedia assistance, it can effectively help teachers and students better grasp classroom content, stimulate their learning interest, cultivate their innovation ability, and effectively transform classroom content into practical actions, thereby better promoting the development of the classroom.

4. Advantages of TPACK in New Teaching Models in Universities

4.1. Development process of instructional design

With the popularization of new media technology, the schools of Shaanxi International Business Research Institute have successfully combined IT, classrooms, learning resources, etc. closely to form a comprehensive teaching method, providing students with the opportunity to explore, learn, and communicate, thus creating a unique teaching environment that enables students to better understand and master the knowledge they have learned [7], and also helps them better apply the theories they have learned. To achieve better learning outcomes. Utilize the Internet and other TPACK tools, such as TPACK, to help teachers better understand and grasp the key points of the course, and be able to use these tools to improve classroom effectiveness. In this way, teachers can better utilize these tools and better guide other teachers, promoting the progress of the entire classroom..

4.2. Construction of TPACK integration mode

Within the framework of TPACK, a key factor is 'context'. According to Dr. Mario Antonio Kelly, [8] TPACK involves a school that is influenced by multiple factors such as physical conditions (including software and hardware infrastructure), family education history, cognitive characteristics, psychology, and class spirit, thereby forming a complete learning atmosphere. The overall operational requirements of TPACK are very clear, so we must attach importance to grasping the situation. At the same time, we also need to equip teachers with TPACK skills [9] and the important roles they play in this operation process.

The structural framework of TPACK is subject to many limitations, such as the selection of course content and the teaching methods of teachers. Therefore, when constructing a TPACK integration model, we

need to deeply integrate TK and CK, and use TPK to create interesting learning situations and stimulate students' learning enthusiasm. Therefore, the TPACK, PCK, TPK, and TCK levels of teachers have a significant impact on their comprehensive and deep integration abilities. In order to effectively improve the quality of undergraduate teaching, we should adopt the TPACK integrated teaching model in order to achieve the best teaching effect.

4.3. Advantages of TPACK integration mode

TPACK integration mode aims to build a comprehensive, comprehensive and highly flexible curriculum system by using the most advanced AI technology, combining the three traditional concepts of "TK", "CK" and "PK", as well as the three cutting-edge elements of "PCK", "TCK" and "TPK", so as to help learners better master the required subjects and better use these elements to improve their learning level. By adopting various methods, such as using testing tools, we can effectively teach information technology [10], providing strong support for improving the quality of education in universities.

4.4. Application of TPACK integration mode in teaching system reform

Based on information-based education, we are committed to achieving better education and learning by enabling learners to have more independent thinking and action. We are working hard to promote TPACK's educational method, making it more widely used in our classrooms, and helping our teachers better achieve information-based education in the context of informatization.

4.5. Teachers' own conditions

Teachers should strive to improve their subject knowledge and skills, and continuously strengthen their ability to integrate knowledge. In addition, they should also conduct more practical exercises in the classroom, develop an effective TPACK architecture based on teaching themes and students' characteristics, and continuously update teaching methods to improve teaching quality.

4.6. Teachers' Self reflection

In order to enhance the professional level of teachers, enhance TPACK skills, and perfectly integrate into the classroom, continuously improve the classroom content. Regularly reflect on classroom content and continuously explore the potential value of the classroom, in order to truly solve problems in the classroom [11].

5. Intelligent mobile terminal teaching

With the development of the Internet, intelligent mobile terminal teaching has become an effective way that is not limited by geography and time. It not only allows teachers to teach better, but also helps students understand knowledge faster. At the same time, high-quality micro course resources can also allow students to easily acquire knowledge outside of class.

5.1. Schools should strengthen institutional construction

Teachers should actively explore new teaching models and innovative methods, and incorporate them into the credit management system to measure their

TPACK teaching ability, and encourage them to integrate these technologies into higher education teaching to improve teaching quality.

In order to better promote the development of universities, we should improve a comprehensive curriculum assessment mechanism in order to objectively and accurately evaluate the quality of teaching. This mechanism should cover teachers' information-based teaching skills, classroom teaching quality, online viewing volume, learners' understanding of the taught topic, and how to organize and implement these mechanisms [12]. Reforming the form of final exams and adopting a comprehensive and comprehensive evaluation system can allow teachers to flexibly guide students based on actual situations, thereby improving their learning status, motivating them to constantly explore and realize their self-worth, greatly improving the classroom atmosphere and greatly enhancing the level of education in the classroom.

Conclusion

The use of TPACK has laid a solid foundation for the implementation of improving the quality of education and teaching. Its operation has greatly benefited teachers' professional quality, technical application, situational mood, and other aspects. Moreover, the operation of TPACK has brought positive impacts to their career. Through in-depth reform of traditional teaching methods, we hope to play a better role in intelligent campuses. This will greatly enhance the abilities of teachers and bring more opportunities for their professional development. We will also combine artificial intelligence theory to bring a new perspective to contemporary teachers, and continuously try and promote this new TPACK integration model through the use of TPACK. This will enable us to better integrate our knowledge into the classroom, thereby better promoting our higher education and achieving better national standards, laying a solid foundation for the development of talent.

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